

Appendix D.1 - Sustainable Business Model Concept Definition Paraphrasing

Legend:		
Goal	Mechanism	Enabler

Paper	Authors	Year	Original Definition	Paraphrased Definition
Conceptualizing a "Sustainability Business Model"	Stubbs and Cocklin	2008	"An SBM requires that organizations treat sustainability as a business strategy in itself, rather than as an add-on." "An SBM requires that shareholders', stakeholders', and organizations' values are aligned around sustainability outcomes, which may only occur when sustainability is institutionalized in society (Jennings & Zandbergen, 1995). According to Bansal (2002), for a practice to be institutionalized in society, the norms must be well defined, which is currently not the case for sustainability." "To fully realize an SBM, modifications to the taxation systems are required to shift the tax burden from "goods," like income and labour, to "bads," like ecological damage and consumption of nonrenewable resources (Costanza, Cumberland, Daly, Goodland, & Norgaard, 1997)." "A SBM Draws on Economic, Environmental and Social Aspects of Sustainability in Defining an Organization's Purpose, A SBM Uses a TBL Approach in Measuring Performance, A SBM Considers the Needs of all Stakeholders Rather Than Giving Priority to Shareholders' Expectations, A SBM Treats Nature as a Stakeholder and Promotes Environmental Stewardship, Sustainability Leaders, or Champions, Drive the Cultural and Structural Changes Necessary to Implement Sustainability, An SBM Encompasses the Systems Perspective As Well As the Firm-Level Perspective"	requires organizations to treat sustainability as a business strategy instead of an add-on. Requires that shareholders, stakeholders and organizations' values are aligned around sustainability outcomes. Norms must be well defined. Uses TBL approach to measure performance, considers needs of all stakeholders rather than giving priority to shareholders' expectations. treats nature as stakeholder. promotes environmental stewardship, sustainability leaders or champions. encompasses systems perspective and firm-level perspective.
Business models for sustainable innovation: state-of-the-art and steps towards a research agenda	Boons and Ludeke-Freund	2013	"Sixteen out of the identified 115 business model articles as well as five book chapters are directly concerned with business models and sustainability issues. Based on these sources, we defined three streams which appear to be most important with regard to sustainable business models: technological, organizational, and social innovation."	important streams for SBMs are technological, organizational and social innovation
Scalability of Sustainable Business Models in Hybrid Organizations	Jablonski	2016	"Ensuring the company's performance in the long term helps to build the so-called sustainable business model that often balances the objectives of stakeholders and shareholders, and that is created by the implemented principles of value-based management and corporate social responsibility." "If we assume that the company's business model is based on the principles of balancing the business from a number of perspectives, it will become a sustainable business model. This definition is also consistent with the assumptions relevant to a sustainable company." "In summary, the sustainable business model building the long-term value of a socially responsible company is a model built by the combined use of the corporate social responsibility and value-based management concepts which guarantees that the needs of shareholders and other stakeholder groups are fulfilled, by balancing the company potential skillfully to generate value allocated in a sustainable way, allowing the continuity of company management. The sustainable business model is a hybrid model, i.e., a model built in a subject- object system."	balances objectives of stakeholders and shareholders. Done by implementing principles of value-based management and CSR, allowing business continuity
An eco-critical perspective on business models: the value triangle as an approach to closing the sustainability gap	Biloslavo et al	2017	"the principles for sustainable BMs proposed by Stubbs and Cocklin (2008) can help us to understand what are their key features: 1. A sustainable BM defines its purpose from economic, environmental and social aspects simultaneously. 2. A sustainable BM uses a triple bottom line approach in measuring performance. 3. A sustainable BM takes into account the needs of several stakeholders and does not favour shareholders. 4. A sustainable BM treats nature as a stakeholder and promotes environmental stewardship. 5. A sustainable BM encompasses the broader system as well as the narrow firm level perspective."	key features: defines purpose from economic, environmental and social aspects simultaneously, uses TBL to measure performance, takes into account needs of diverse stakeholders, doesn't favor shareholders, treats nature as stakeholder, promotes env stewardship, encompasses broader system level perspective

<p>Business Model Innovation for Sustainability: Towards a Unified Perspective for Creation of Sustainable Business Models</p>	<p>Evans et al</p>	<p>2017</p>	<p>"The purpose of this paper is to present a unified perspective for innovation towards SBMs leading to better economic, environmental and social performance of organizations." "Hence, treating society and nature as stakeholders of the firm are important elements of the conceptualization of SBMs (Stubbs and Cocklin, 2008)." "To summarize, the scope of value should include not only economic transactions but also relationships, exchanges and interactions that take place among stakeholders (Allee, 2011) and that can be represented by value flows (Den Ouden, 2012). Identifying all the value flows among stakeholders, including the natural environment and society as primary stakeholders, can reveal opportunities for business model innovation. Proposition 1. Sustainable value incorporates economic, social and environmental benefits conceptualized as value forms. Proposition 2. SBMs require a system of sustainable value flows among multiple stakeholders including the natural environment and society as primary stakeholders." "Mutual value creation in SBMs, therefore, requires systemic consideration of a wide set of stakeholders who have a stake and responsibility in the value creation system. Proposition 3. SBMs require a value network with a new purpose, design and governance. Proposition 4. SBMs require a systemic consideration of stakeholder interests and responsibilities for mutual value creation."</p>	<p>aims for better economic, environmental and social performance. Treat society and nature as stakeholders of the firm. Value scopes includes relationships, exchanges and interactions between stakeholders on top of economic transactions. Proposition 1. Sustainable value incorporates economic, social and environmental benefits conceptualized as value forms. Proposition 2. SBMs require a system of sustainable value flows among multiple stakeholders including the natural environment and society as primary stakeholders." "Mutual value creation in SBMs, therefore, requires systemic consideration of a wide set of stakeholders who have a stake and responsibility in the value creation system. Proposition 3. SBMs require a value network with a new purpose, design and governance. Proposition 4. SBMs require a systemic consideration of stakeholder interests and responsibilities for mutual value creation</p>
<p>Transforming sustainability challenges into competitive advantage: Multiple case studies kaleidoscope converging into sustainable business models</p>	<p>Morioka et al</p>	<p>2017</p>	<p>"sustainable business models (SBM's) attempt to go beyond isolated social and environmental initiatives and systematically integrate sustainability into business (Bocken et al., 2014; Boons and Lüdeke-Freund, 2013), in which corporate sustainability concepts shape decision making processes (Stubbs and Cocklin, 2008). SBM can be seen as a construct to support deploying corporate sustainability strategies into sustainable operations and processes." "our work definition is that SBM is a representation of business elements, their interrelations and the systemic context that enable sustainable value exchange with stakeholders towards corporate sustainability performance, translating and providing feedback between corporate strategy and operations." "Variations of the term SBM (Bocken et al., 2014; Boons et al., 2013; Boons and Lüdeke-Freund, 2013) have been also used, such as business model for sustainability (Schaltegger et al., 2016a), sustainability business model (Stubbs and Cocklin, 2008), flourishing/strongly sustainable business model (Upward and Jones, 2016), truly sustainable business models (Dyllick and Muff, 2016) and also as normative business model (Randles and Laasch, 2016). Despite specific nuances that differentiate these concepts, the present research uses the term SBM to represent the common idea of these concepts of a business model that systematically integrates corporate sustainability principles into organizational strategy and operations." "The SBM archetypes bring an variety of opportunities for organizations to innovate their business logics (Bocken et al., 2014). The archetypes include: maximise material and energy efficiency; create value from 'waste'; substitute with renewable and natural processes; deliver functionality rather than ownership; adopt a stewardship role; encourage sufficiency; re-purpose the business for society/ environment; and develop scale-up solutions. These archetypes, however, can be criticized as they do not guarantee that the business is systematically sustainable."</p>	<p>integrate sustainability into business. Construct to deploy corporate sustainability strategies into sustainable operations and processes. SBM and BmFs are the same.</p>
<p>Value uncaptured perspective for sustainable business model innovation</p>	<p>M. Yang, S. Evans, D. Vladimirova, P. Rana</p>	<p>2017</p>	<p>Sustainable Business Models are defined by Lüdeke-Freund (2010) as "a business model that creates competitive advantage through superior customer value and contributes to the sustainable development of the company and society". This recognises that the core of a sustainable business is still creating and delivering customer value (Chesbrough, 2010, Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010, Teece, 2010, Zott et al., 2011), but in which the environmental and social benefits are embedded.</p>	<p>contributes to sustainable development of company and society. Embeds environmental and social benefits to creation and delivery of customer value</p>
<p>Embracing the variety of sustainable business models: A prolific field of research and a future research agenda</p>	<p>Dentchev et al</p>	<p>2018</p>	<p>"SBMs are defined by Schaltegger et al. (2016a, p. 6) as helpful tools for "describing, analyzing, managing, and communicating (i) a company's sustainable value proposition to its customers, and all other stakeholders, (ii) how it creates and delivers this value, (iii) and how it captures economic value while maintaining or regenerating natural, social, and economic capital beyond its organizational boundaries."</p>	<p>a sustainable BM "helps describing, analyzing, managing and communicating (i) a company's sustainable value proposition to its customers and all other stakeholders, (ii) how it creates and delivers this value, (iii) and how it captures economic value while maintaining or regenerating natural, social and economic capital beyond its organizational boundaries"</p>

The Competitiveness of Firms through the Sustainable Business Model: A Decade of Research	Di Tullio et al	2018	"The sbm is a business model that creates a competitive advantage (Lüdeke-Freund, 2010) following a logic that integrates economic, environmental, and social aspects, considering present and future generations (Schneider, 2015). In the sbm, sustainability concepts shape the driving force of the firm and its decision making (Stubbs, Cocklin 2008), enabling social entrepreneurs to create social value and maximize social profit (Boons, Lüdeke-Freund 2013). An sbm can serve as a vehicle to coordinate technological and social innovations with system-level sustainability (Bocken et al., 2014), implementing principles of value-based management and csr (Jablonski, 2016)." Evans et al. (2017) develop five propositions that support the creation of sbms from a unified perspective, as follows: sustainable value incorporates economic, social, and environmental benefits conceptualized as value forms; sbms require a system of sustainable value flows among multiple stakeholders, including the natural environment and society as primary stakeholders; sbms require a value network with a new purpose, design, and governance; sbms require the systemic consideration of stakeholder interests and responsibilities for mutual value creation; and internalizing externalities through a pss enables innovation towards sbms. The core of an sbm is a sustainable value proposition that goes beyond customers (Biloslavo et al., 2018), reflects a business-society dialog concerning the balance of economic, ecological, and social needs (Boons, Lüdeke-Freund 2013), could be viewed as the combination of three elements – stakeholder network, sustainability problem, and product/service-, and could be designed following three steps – Testing, Thinking, and Talking – (Baldassarre et al., 2017)."	Integrates economic, environmental and social aspects. Considers present and future generations. Sustainability shapes driving force of firm. Its core is a sustainable VP that goes beyond customers and balances economic, ecological and and social needs. Evans et al. (2017) develop five propositions that support the creation of sbms from a unified perspective, as follows: sustainable value incorporates economic, social, and environmental benefits conceptualized as value forms; sbms require a system of sustainable value flows among multiple stakeholders, including the natural environment and society as primary stakeholders; sbms require a value network with a new purpose, design, and governance; sbms require the systemic consideration of stakeholder interests and responsibilities for mutual value creation; and internalizing externalities through a pss enables innovation towards sbms.
Sustainable business models: Providing a more holistic perspective	Lozano	2018	"From the above discussions, the elements in a BM thus consist of: • Material resources and energy. The inputs are transformed in the company through operations and production (using technology) into output products and/or services. These inputs and outputs are part of the supply chain (see Bocken et al., 2014; Lozano, 2012). • Stakeholders that affect and are affected by the company (see Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Lozano, 2012; Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008). • Economic value (intrinsic to the material inputs and explicit to the output products/services), and value added in the company through resource efficiency and transformation (see Bocken et al., 2014; Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008). • Human resources that enter and leave the company (see Penrose, 1959). • Tangible resources (e.g., infrastructure, plant equipment, land and natural resources, waste products, and finished goods) (see Penrose, 1959). • The (intrinsic) environmental value of the materials and energy and of the output products/services (implied by Bocken et al., 2014; Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008)."	SBM and BMFS are the same. Another name can be SOBM but this would imply view that it's from BMs to sustainability.
The sustainable business model pattern taxonomy – 45 patterns to support sustainability-oriented business model innovation	Ludeke-freund et al	2018	"A sustainable business model is about creating significantly increased positive effects and/or significantly reduced negative effects for the natural environment and society through changes in the way a company and its network create, deliver, and capture value (e.g., Bocken et al., 2014; Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008; Wells, 2013). Ideally speaking, SBMs allow companies to pursue sustainability through the deliberate alignment of their business interests with contributions to a sustainable development of the natural environment and society (see the definition based on Schaltegger et al., 2016a, in the introduction). At the heart of such a business model is a value proposition that is valuable to both ers and other stakeholders who might otherwise be directly or indirectly affected by a company's activities. "	is about creating significantly increased positive effects an/or significantly reduced negative effects for the natural environment and society. Done by changing how company and its network create, deliver and capture value. Pursue sustainability by deliberate alignment of business interests with contributions to sustainable dev of environment and society. at heart of SBM is a VP that is valuable both to shareholders and stakeholders who might be indirectly affected by activities
Incumbents and business model innovation for the sharing economy: Implications for sustainability	Ciulli and Kolk	2019	"sustainable business models (Bocken et al., 2014), i.e. business models which, beside financial value, also create social and/or environmental value.""	BM that create social and/or environmental value in addition to financial value

Business Models For Industrial Symbiosis: A Taxonomy Focused on the Form of Governance	Fraccascia et al	2019	"Facing the challenge to pursue sustainable development, firms are looking for new ways to do business delivering at the same time environmental and social benefits (e.g., Schaltegger et al., 2016). Sustainable business models are proposed to help firms in this regard (e.g., Boons and Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Manninen et al., 2018)." "Sustainable business models "create competitive advantage through superior customer value and contribute to a sustainable development of the company and society" (Lüdeke-Freund, 2010, p. 23). Therefore, compared to a classical business model, the value proposition of a sustainable business model includes value for society and natural environment in addition to the economic value for the firm (Boons and Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Manninen et al., 2018; Schaltegger et al., 2016)."	pursue sustainable development. Deliver environmental and social benefits at same time. VP includes value for society and natural environment in addition to economic value to firm.
Addressing the design-implementation gap of sustainable business models by prototyping: A tool for planning and executing small-scale pilots	Baldassarre et al	2020	"Recent work conceptualized SBMs ("a value proposition that provides economic, environmental and social value; a supply chain and a customer interface that allows stakeholders and customers to act responsibly; a financial model that reflects an appropriate distribution of costs and benefits across stakeholders") (Boons and Lüdeke-Freund, 2013)"	a value proposition that provides economic, environmental and social value. A supply chain and a customer interface. A financial model. Allows stakeholders and customers to act responsibly, distributes costs/benefits across them
Linking Sustainable Business Models to Socio-Ecological Resilience Through Cross-Sector Partnerships: A Complex Adaptive Systems View	Dentoni et al	2020	"A myriad of business models nowadays aim (or claim) to be sustainable by creating social and environmental value and delivering net-positive impacts to society and the natural environment. Such "sustainable" business models describe, analyze, manage, and communicate how value is created and captured "while maintaining or regenerating natural, social, and economic capital beyond its organizational boundaries" (Schaltegger, Hansen, & Lüdeke-Freund, 2016, p. 6)." "To achieve their sustainability aspirations, sustainable business models depend on "collaboration across a wider set of stakeholders in an industrial system" (Bocken et al., 2015, p. 67) and must consider the effects on the plurality of agents embedded in their socio-ecological system (Pedersen et al., 2019; Upward & Jones, 2016). The cross-sectoral nature of the partnership component of sustainable business models clearly sets them apart from other business models where companies mainly collaborate with their supply chain actors or other industry players to create economic value (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). In sustainable business models, companies tend to partner with public and nonprofit actors to create or prevent the destruction of social or environmental value (Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008)." "What distinguishes sustainable business models from the traditional business models is not only their aspiration to create social and environmental value for a wide range of stakeholders but also the collaboration among stakeholders with diverse backgrounds and values (Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Pedersen et al., 2019; Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008)."	describe, analyze, manage and communicate how value is created and captured while maintaining or regenerating natural, social and economic capbital beyond org boundaries. Rely on collaboration across wide set of stakeholders in system. They are cross-sectoral which distinguishes them from other BMs. orgs tend to partner with public or nonprofit actors.
Digital sustainable entrepreneurship: A business model perspective on embedding digital technologies for social and environmental value creation	Gregori and Holzmann	2020	"While the commercial notion of value that evolves around financial gain characterizes conventional business models, sustainable business models go beyond mere financial profit (Bocken et al., 2014; Schaltegger et al., 2016) and also emphasize values and beliefs of an environmental and a social logic (Laasch, 2018; Stubbs, 2017a)." "This is of particular importance for sustainable business models, which are fraught with additional efforts in managing external relationships because they need to include a wider range of diverse stakeholders (Evans et al., 2017; Stubbs and Cocklin, 2008)."	go beyond financial profit and emphasize values and beliefs of an environmental and social logic. Need to include a wider range of diverse stakeholders, requiring efforts in managing external relationships

Sustainable Business Model Based on Digital Twin Platform Network: The Inspiration from Haier's Case Study in China	Li et al	2020	"A sustainable business model is economically, environmentally and socially sustainable [3]: it must help companies not only achieve fundamental reductions in energy and material consumption but also obtain financial and social benefits while providing the necessary products or services." "From the perspective of system theory, the sustainable business model can construct a triple bottom line approach to define corporate goals and measure performance, which includes a wide range of stakeholders, especially the environment and society [23]. Steve Evans et al. [1] comprehensively summarized the forms of the economic, environmental and social benefits included in sustainable business model. Economic benefits include profit and a return on investment; environmental benefits include unit energy consumption, and renewable resources use; social benefits include community development and labor standards." "Combining the above SBM concepts, and based on the definition of business model value, the sustainable business model is defined as a model for enterprises to create, transfer and acquire economic, social and environmental values sustainably. It can seek a balance among economic, social and environmental benefits, and obtain wider support by satisfying the demands of stakeholders, so as to promote the sustainable development of enterprises and ultimately promote overall economic, environmental and social sustainable development."	economically, environmentally and socially sustainability. Must help achieve fundamental reductions in eneergy and material consumption and to achieve financial and social benefits. Corporate goals and performance measurment based on TBL. a model for enterprises to create, transfer and acquire economic, social and environmental values sustainably. It can seek a balance among economic, social and environmental benefits, and obtain wider support by satisfying the demands of stakeholders, so as to promote the sustainable development of enterprises and ultimately promote overall economic, environmental and social sustainable development
Sustainable entrepreneurship, innovation, and business models: Integrative framework and propositions for future research	Ludeke-freund	2020	"Building on these assumptions, Schaltegger, Hansen, and Lüdeke-Freund (2016), p. 6) propose the following definition of a sustainable business model (used interchangeably with "business model for sustainability"): "A business model for sustainability helps describing, analysing, managing, and communicating (i) a company's sustainable value proposition to its customers, and all other stakeholders, (ii) how it creates and delivers this value, (iii) and how it captures economic value while maintaining or regenerating natural, social, and economic capital beyond its organisational boundaries.""	SBM and BMfs are used interchangeably in literature. A business model for sustainability helps describing, analysing, managing, and communicating (i) a company's sustainable value proposition to its customers, and all other stakeholders, (ii) how it creates and delivers this value, (iii) and how it captures economic value while maintaining or regenerating natural, social, and economic capital beyond its organisational boundaries.
The Role of Linked Legitimacy in Sustainable Business Model Development	Press et al	2020	"In general, the concept of SBMs builds off that of BMs, however, SBMs include an awareness of negative environmental and social externalities from organizational activities and a desire to address them (Teece 2010; Starik and Kanashiro, 2013). There is agreement that in SBMs, sustainability means value must be created along triple bottom line measures of the firm's performance, those that address environmental, economic and social issues (Stubbs and Cocklin 2008, 119; Elkington, 1997; Bansal 2002)."	include an awareness of negative environmental and social externalities and want to address them. Sustainability means value creation along TBL measures of firm's performance which address environemntal, economic and social issues
Anatomy of sustainable business model innovation	Shakeel et al	2020	"The definition in the literature perceive SBM as a modification concept related to specific characteristics and goals and either (1) incorporates goals, conceptions, and principles aiming at sustainability or (2) include sustainability aspects into value propositions, creation and delivery, and capture (Evans et al., 2017). The literature streams seem too diverse to the conceptualisation of SBM. One stream focuses on defining it (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018) while others are struggling to align it with the strategic organisational architecture of value proposition, creation and delivery, and capture (Boons and Ludeke-Freund, 2013)."	either (1) incorporates goals, conceptions, and principles aiming at sustainability or (2) include sustainability aspects into value propositions, creation and delivery, and capture
The sustainability performances of sustainable business models	Alonso-Martinez et al.	2021	"Sustainable Business Models (SBMs) are innovative architectures for the creation, delivery and capture of value, which place environmental and social goals at the core of the business and orient firms' activities (Stubbs, 2019).SBMs have the potential to solve social and environmental problems in new, more profitable ways by creating competitive advantage and value for society at large (Boons and Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Schaltegger et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2017)." "a Sustainable Business Model (SBM) is "about creating significantly increased positive effects and/or significantly reduced negative effects for the natural environment and society through changes in the way a company and its network create, deliver, and capture value" (Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2018: 147)." "Based on a comprehensive review of the literature and practices, nine SBM archetypes are proposed and further classified in three higher-order groupings – depending on the major focus of the SBM innovation (environmental, social, or economic). Each of the SBMs identified is expected to create value in a different manner, putting more or less emphasis on the environmental, social or economic dimension (Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2018a)." (see table 1)	innovative architectures, place environmental and social goals at core of business. Is about creating increased positive effects and/or significantly reduced negative effects for environment and society. Each SBM type puts more or less emphasis on the 3 dimensions
Circular economy as a driver to sustainable businesses	Barros et al	2021	"more sustainable business models have been discussed in the last few years (Bocken et al., 2014), especially embracing the concept of circular economy towards circular business models (e.g. (Urbanati et al., 2017; Nußholz, 2017; Leipold and Petit-Boix, 2018; Salvador et al., 2021a))"	CBM are type of SBM

Investigating Circular Business Model Innovation through Keywords Analysis	Bigliardi and Filippelli	2021	<p>"The prerequisite for responding to such socio-ecological megatrends is the introduction of a sustainable business model". "(SBM) that defines the company's financial and economic objectives as well as social and environmental ones [18]. The sustainable business model is a conventional business model modified in order to integrate the sustainability dimension into the organization. Specifically, what makes a business model sustainable is the presence of practices and principles that enable the company to achieve its sustainability ambitions and the integration of sustainability into the three dimensions of value proposition, value creation and delivery, and value capture [18]. Stubbs and Cocklin [19] point out that a sustainable business model combines the creation of measurable environmental and social value with economic value, considering the environment and the society as key stakeholders to be addressed." "Several subcategories, or archetypes, of sustainable business models exist, e.g., product-service systems, base of the pyramid, and circular business models [20]"</p>	<p>describes company's objectives (economic, social, environmental). Is a conventional BM modified to integrate sustainability dimension into the organization. Bm is SBM if presence of practices and principles that enable achievement of sustainability ambitions and integration of sustainability into dimensions of value. consider environment and society as key stakeholders. archetypes of SBM are e.g. PSS, BoP, CBM</p>
Classification of Sustainable Business Models: a Literature Review and a Map of Their Impact on the Sustainable Development Goals	Boffa and Maffei	2021	<p>"The SBM will define sustainable value creation mechanisms while ensuring profitability [14,16]. The SBM requires companies to make sustainability the center of their business strategy [17]. According to [18] sustainability is integrated into the organization's business strategy by creating an internal commitment to sustainability." "SBM's applications have sustainable value propositions as primary source of a company's competitive advantage. The value propositions in SBM allow for social and environmental benefits creation." "This is supported by a sustainability-oriented business strategy included in the SBM. [...] The strategic agenda in organizations will be formulated to include sustainability-oriented goals, creating an internal commitment sustainability."</p>	<p>makes sustainability the center of business strategy by creating internal commitment to sustainability. Sustainability value propositions are primary competitive advantage. Creates social and environmental benefits</p>
Sustainable business model: A review and framework development	Goni et al	2021	<p>"Geissdoerfer et al. (2016) defined a sustainable business model as a "simplified representation of the elements, the interrelationship between these elements, and the interactions with its stakeholders that an organisational unit uses to create, deliver, capture, and exchange sustainable value". The main idea of the SBM concept is to modify the conventional business model by embedding sustainability into the value chains of an organisation (Geissdoerfer et al. 2018)." "SBM has three unique features that make them different from conventional business models. i. The objective of SBMs is to generate value for multiple stakeholders, society, and the environment (Abdelkafi and Tauscher 2016). ii. The SBM field envisages non-financial forms of value, such as social and environmental values (Bocken et al. 2014). iii. In addition to considering value creation, the SBM field also contemplates value destroyed to realise the negative effect on society and environment (e.g. depletion of resources or social dislocation), and value uncaptured (e.g. reusable components of damaged tools) (de Pádua Pieroni et al. 2018). These features distinguish SBM from traditional business models that focus on profit, which means that they are different capabilities compared to other types of business models, as stated in the literature." "Bocken et al. (2014) observed the integration of some concepts into SBMs, including closedloop thinking, natural capitalism, social enterprises, product-service systems (PSS), and new economy concepts (e.g. Blue Economy). This notion points out that a business model has different definitions and viewpoints." "Geissdoerfer et al. (2018) mentioned that a sustainable business model could be seen as a modification of the concept of a conventional business model with specific characteristics: (1) integrating the sustainability concepts, principles, and goals into SBM and (2) integrating sustainability concept into the value chain." "This study has proposed a new perspective of the SBM. The generalisation that can be drawn from the results is: i. An SBM needs to consider nine significant aspects, including sustainability pillars, circular economy, information technology, value chain, core values, value creation, organisational values, performance management, and stakeholder engagement. ii. The circular economy aspect should be incorporated into SBM to uncover new ways of providing value to stakeholders and systematically explore economic value throughout the product life cycle to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of resources. iii. Aspects of information technology and corporate performance management are generally not integrated into the SBM; however, they are essential to support effective implementation of the SBM. iv. The role of information technology is to manage and control ecosystem processes at all levels, especially in integrating, analysing, and disseminating data and information about resources. v. Performance management is an essential aspect to assess the performance of SBM implementation."</p>	<p>embeds sustainability into value chains of organization. Aims to generate value for multiple stakeholders, society and environment, generates financial and non-financial value forms, contemplates both value creation and value destroyed and value uncaptured. An SBM needs to consider nine significant aspects, including sustainability pillars, circular economy, information technology, value chain, core values, value creation, organisational values, performance management, and stakeholder engagement. iii. Aspects of information technology and corporate performance management are generally not integrated into the SBM; however, they are essential to support effective implementation of the SBM. iv. The role of information technology is to manage and control ecosystem processes at all levels, especially in integrating, analysing, and disseminating data and information about resources. v. Performance management is an essential aspect to assess the performance of SBM implementation."</p>

The Business Model in Sustainability Transitions: A Conceptualization	Hernandez-Chea et al	2021	"sustainable business models take into account ecological, social and financial concerns embedded into business activities, as well as interactions with a wide range of stakeholders to implement activities [8,9]. Sustainable business models differ from dominant unsustainable ones (e.g., the linear economy business model) by either incorporating concepts to pursue sustainability and integrating sustainability or circularity into their value proposition, value creation and delivery activities, and/or value capture [7,10]." "SBMs facilitate sustainable transition pathways, for example, through delivering functionality (through leasing or rental) rather than ownership, reduction in waste through buy-back schemes, and the use of renewable or recycled material in products and processes. SBMs, therefore, help in directing firms' activity to move in coherence with the idea of the circular economy [20]." "Firms pursue sustainability by aligning their business strategies to benefit society and the environment. The starting point for adopting a SBM is the development of a viable vision and purpose [8,83]. A viable vision embeds a desired sustainable impact—for people, planet, and profit—to achieve in the long-term, and also a motivating force as inspiration to improve well-being and environment issues [84]. [...] Furthermore, firms moving towards SBM partially or completely substitute existing unsustainable value propositions with sustainable products and services [37]. For example, firms in the mobility sector pursue product-service systems to create better sustainability outcomes by using more sustainable modes of transportation [21] and, e.g., substituting gasoline vehicles with electric ones, to contribute to mitigating the present carbon crisis [86]."	accounts for ecological, social and financial concerns as well as interactions with wide range of stakeholders to implement its activities. Incorporate concepts to pursue sustainability and integrating sustainability or circularity into their VP/creation/delivery/capture. long-term perspective. firms with SBMS partially or fully replace unsustainable value propositions with sustainable products and services
Industry 4.0 and sustainable development: A systematic mapping of triple bottom line, Circular Economy and Sustainable Business Models perspectives	Khan et al	2021	"Furthermore, sustainable business models (SBMs) encompass the TBL and account for multiple parties alongside the environment and society at large (Bocken et al., 2014). They are essential in directing and implementing innovative business processes for sustainability by adopting circular economy (CE) strategies such as narrowing, slowing and closing the resource loop (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017), making them key drivers of competitive advantage (Bocken et al., 2014) and overall SD." "In this paper, we follow Machado et al. (2020) and explain SBMs as tools that maintain a balance between social, environmental and economic needs while still preserving value proposition in terms of creating new jobs, saving costs and reducing adverse environmental impacts (Boons and Lüdeke-Freund, 2013)."	encompass TBL and account for multiple stakeholders alongside environment and society at large. Tools that maintain balance between social, env and economic needs while preserving value proposition in terms of creating new jobs saving costs and reducing adverse env impacts
Collaborative Sustainable Business Models: Understanding Organizations Partnering for Community Sustainability	Ordinez-Porce et al	2021	"Sustainable business models (SBMs) entail a logic of not only creating economic value for organizations, but also social and ecological value for society and the natural environment (Abdelkafi & Täuscher, 2016; Schaltegger, Hansen, & Lüdeke-Freund, 2016)." "SBMs describe how value is created, delivered and captured, while maintaining or regenerating natural, social, and/or economic capital beyond the boundaries of a single firm (Schaltegger, Lüdeke-Freund, & Hansen, 2016), with sustainability as a central concern to their strategic decision-making processes (Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008)."	entail logic of creating social and ecological value for society and natural environment on top of economic value for organization. describe how value is created, delivered and captured, while maintaining or regenerating natural, social, and/or economic capital beyond the boundaries of a single firm , with sustainability as a central concern to their strategic decision-making processes
Valuing Value in Innovation Ecosystems: How Cross-Sector Actors Overcome Tensions in Collaborative Sustainable Business Model Development	Oskam et al	2021	"Sustainable business models are a special type of business models that distinguish themselves through the application of four basic design principles (Breuer et al., 2018). First, a sustainability-oriented orientation in itself is a key requirement, intentionally including sustainability goals and values that provide a shared normative reference for the collaborating actors (Breuer et al., 2018). Second, sustainable business model development includes a broad notion of value beyond a mere economic value. Actors negotiate about the creation and capture of social, environmental, and economic value to improve sustainability (Breuer et al., 2018; Evans et al., 2017; Schaltegger et al., 2016; Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008). Third, sustainable business model development requires a systemic approach that entails life cycle thinking, design of product-service systems, and reflection on the potential outcomes of the new business model (Breuer et al., 2018). Fourth, sustainable business model development not only considers customers or end users but also addresses the interests of a large variety of actors and stakeholders, including nature and society (Breuer et al., 2018; Evans et al., 2017; Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2016; Schaltegger et al., 2016)."	distinguished based on application of four design principles: sustainability orientation and intentionality, value beyond just economic (social, environmental) to improve sustainability, require systemic approach that entails life-cycle thinking and design of PSS and reflection on potential outcomes of the NBM, and consider interests of a large variety of actors and stakeholders including nature and society
Value creation and appropriation in economic, social, and environmental domains: Recognizing and resolving the institutionalized asymmetries	Ritala et al	2021	"Business models that take into account the tradeoffs and possibilities of value creation and appropriation in the economic, social, and environmental domains (Boons and Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Bocken et al., 2014; Bocken, 2015; Ritala et al., 2018)" "Ideal types of sustainable business models would integrate social, environmental, and economic issues simultaneously and create positive value and reduce negative value through business activities (Stubbs and Cocklin, 2008)."	take into account tradeoffs and possibilities of value creation and appropriation in economic, social and environmental domains. Integrate social, environmental and economic issues simultaneous to create positive value and reduce negative value of business activities

Design principles for sustainability assessments in the business model innovation process	Bhatnagar et al	2022	"These models define the rationale of how a company does business to create social, environmental, and economic value." "An SBM can be defined as a means that "helps describing, analyzing, managing, and communicating (i) a company's sustainable value proposition to its customers, and all other stakeholders, (ii) how it creates and delivers this value, (iii) and how it captures economic value while maintaining or regenerating natural, social, and economic capital beyond its organizational boundaries" (Schaltegger et al., 2016, p. 6). This definition extends the traditional business model concept, by also taking into account the firm's social and environmental activities and their impacts (Schaltegger et al., 2012; Breuer et al., 2018). It requires a focus on aligning the interests of a diversity of stakeholder groups, including customers, other societal stakeholders, and a network of business organizations (Bocken et al., 2014, 2018)."	define rationale of how companies do business to create social, environmental and economic value. Requires focus on aligning interests of diverse stakeholder groups
Sustainable business model innovation and scaling through collaboration	Ciulli et al	2022	"business models that "create significant positive and/or significantly reduced negative impacts for the environment and/or society" (Bocken et al., 2014, p. 44)." "Over the years, different terms have been used to refer to business models that aim to create environmental and/or social value, with varying degrees of emphasis on the 'non-financial' aspects. Examples include "sustainable business model" (Bocken et al., 2014), "business model for sustainability" (Schaltegger et al., 2016a), "social business model" (Yunus et al., 2010), "Bottom of the Pyramid business model" (Kolk et al., 2014) or "circular business model" (Urbinati et al., 2017). While "sustainable business model" and "business model for sustainability" have been often interpreted as synonymous, the other concepts represent "different subcategories [...] for sustainable business models" (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018, p. 403), by zooming in on specific types of non-economic value creation (e.g., circularity for environmental value creation, value creation for the poor)." "The most widely adopted one is from Schaltegger et al. (2016a, p. 6): a sustainable business model "helps describing, analyzing, managing, and communicating (i) a company's sustainable value proposition to its customers, and all other stakeholders, (ii) how it creates and delivers this value, (iii) and how it captures economic value while maintaining or regenerating natural, social, and economic capital beyond its organizational boundaries"."	create significant positive and/or significantly reduced negative impacts for the environment and/or society. SBM and BMFs are synonymous. CBM, social BM, BoP are different subcategories of SBM
Untangling business model outcomes, impacts and value	Dembek et al	2022	"From a sustainability perspective, a sustainable business model (SBM) has been defined as a business model that 'creates, delivers, and captures economic, social and environmental value. The decision-making logic of a BMfS [(business model for sustainability)] is not focused only on profit generation, but rather it considers society and environment as essential and most influential stakeholders' (Preghenella & Battistella, 2021, p. 2)." "Another defining characteristic of SBMs is that they aim not only to create value but also to positively impact the environment and societies in which they operate (Lüdeke-Freund, 2020)."	BM that creates, delivers and captures economic, social and environmental value. SBM is BMfS. Considers society and environment as essential and most influential stakeholders. Positively impact environment and societies where they operate
Business research for sustainable development: How does sustainable business model research reflect doughnut economics?	Hausdorf and Timm	2022	"Schaltegger et al. (2016, p. 6) propose that 'a business model for sustainability helps describing, analyzing, managing, and communicating (i) a company's sustainable value proposition to its customers, and all other stakeholders, (ii) how it creates and delivers this value, (iii) and how it captures economic value while maintaining or regenerating natural, social, and economic capital beyond its organizational boundaries'." "We found that 'create to regenerate' is the most widespread principle among the publications in our sample. A total of 36 of 40 articles in our sample reflect the principle through concrete concepts."	Schaltegger et al. (2016, p. 6) propose that 'a business model for sustainability helps describing, analyzing, managing, and communicating (i) a company's sustainable value proposition to its customers, and all other stakeholders, (ii) how it creates and delivers this value, (iii) and how it captures economic value while maintaining or regenerating natural, social, and economic capital beyond its organizational boundaries'
Exploring the impact of sustainable value proposition on firm performance	Ilyas and Osiyevskyy	2022	"In sum, organizations adopt sustainable practices in the components of their business models that set their business models as sustainable in comparison with others." "In existing research on sustainable business models, scholars emphasize the creation of economic, social, and environmental value as the main objective (Laasch, 2018; Sa ríchez & Ricart, 2010; Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008). Also, many scholars study the concept of sustainable business model and discuss various definitions of the term (Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Schaltegger et al., 2016), archetypes (Bocken, Rana, & Short, 2015), as well as patterns (Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2018) of a sustainable business model based on the inclusion of different dimensions of sustainability in the conventional business model. Furthermore, the literature analyzed the process of adopting sustainability in the conventional business model and its components (i.e., sustainable value proposition) (Laasch, 2018; Patala et al., 2016). Also, the role of organizational learning and adaptation (Roome & Louche, 2016), stakeholder needs (Sa ríchez & Ricart, 2010; Seelos, 2014), and technological and social innovation (Davies & Chambers, 2018; Dobson, Boone, Andries, & Daou, 2018; McDermott, Kurucz, & Colbert, 2018) during the evolution and transformation of sustainable business model was widely discussed. Furthermore, from the previous literature on sustainable business models (Dentchev et al., 2018; Evans et al., 2017; Lüdeke-Freund & Dembek, 2017; Schaltegger et al., 2016), it is emerging that "companies developing, and implementing SBMs (sustainable business models) increase the likelihood of being financially viable and contributing to sustainable development" (Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2018, p. 147)."	sustainable practices in components of the BM. Creation of economic, social and environmental value is main objective. Contribute to sustainable development

Dynamic sustainable business modelling: exploring the dynamics of business model components considering the product development framework	Maresova et al	2022	"A sustainable business model, considering sustainable values, emphasises the joint creation of social and environmental benefits along with profits. Sustainable business models include sustainability as an integral part of a company's value proposition and logic of value creation. Sustainable business models require a system of sustainable value streams among stakeholders, including the natural environment and society as the main stakeholders (Geissdoerfer, Vladimirova, and Evans 2018)."	considers sustainable values and emphasizes joint creation of social and environmental benefits along with profits. Sustainability is integral part of company's VP and value creation logic. Requires a system of sustainable value streams among stakeholders include natural environment and society as main stakeholders
Towards Systematic Sustainable Business Model Innovation: What Can We Learn from Business Model Innovation	Minatogawa et al	2022	"A business model for sustainability, also known as a sustainable business model (SBM), represents how a company creates, delivers, and captures value while generating positive effects and/or reducing negative impacts on the environment and society [5]. "A sustainable company creates benefits for all stakeholders while acting in the preservation of the environment and contributing to people's lives [28]. Based on this definition and considering the abovementioned SBM definition, we can affirm that sustainable companies need an SBM. For example, it is not enough for a sustainable company to deliver a new ecofriendly product (as a value to its customers). If its value creation processes, i.e., how the company develops and distributes this product, harm the environment, how can it be considered sustainable? If the value capture, i.e., how the company obtains returns on the delivered product, causes negative social impacts, such as encouraging excessive consumerism [29], how can it be considered sustainable?"	BmFS is SBM. Represents how company creates, delivers, captures value while generating positive effects and/or reducing negative impacts on environment and society. Creates benefits for all stakeholders while preserving environment and contributing to people's lives. all value dynamics must adhere to sustainability principles
Green Business Models: definitions, types, and life cycle analysis	Solesvik et al	2022	"Sustainable business models include three dimensions, i.e. environmental, social and economic (Prause, 2015). Some authors call sustainable business models triple bottom line business models (Khan et al., 2021), because the triple bottom line is the main theory of sustainability, and those triple bottoms are environmental, social, and economic pillars. Notably, all three vectors of sustainability are equally important."	include three dimensions: environmental, social, economic. All three are equally important
Does the combination of sustainable business model patterns lead to truly sustainable business models? Critical analysis of existing frameworks and extensions	Abdelkafi et al	2023	"sustainable business models (SBMs), in other words business models that are not only ecologically, but also economically and socially sustainable (e.g., Abdelkafi and Hansen 2018; Abdelkafi and Täuscher 2016). "business models can be clustered in different groups (Lüdeke-Freund et al. 2018b): mainly economic, social-economic, social, mainly ecological, and integrative. Hence, most SBM patterns do not cover all dimensions of the TBL, making a combination of patterns (archetypes) required." "we argue that the set of SBM archetypes proposed in literature should be taken with criticism because of two reasons. First, some SBM patterns such as "Maximize material and energy efficiency" in Bocken et al. (2014) do not really reflect ways of doing business, but rather point to operational efficiencies that many firms, if not all—sustainable or unsustainable—aim for. This can result in rather "seemingly sustainable" business models. Second, recent empirical research that aims to evaluate the sustainability value of different SBM patterns found that SBM patterns do not have equal contributions to sustainability. For example, in the context of Product Service Systems (PSS), Yang and Evans (2019) show that result-oriented PSS exhibits a higher sustainability value than use-oriented or product-oriented PSS, whereas PSS alone does not significantly improve social sustainability."	ecologically, economically and socially sustainable. Most SBM patterns don't cover all dimensions of TBL, making combination of patterns required
Digital sustainable business models: Using digital technology to integrate ecological sustainability into the core of business models	Bottcher et al	2023	"Sustainable BMs are designed around economic, ecological, and social value, also known as the triple bottom line (Elkington, 1998; Evans et al., 2017; Schaltegger et al., 2016; Upward & Jones, 2015). This is also reflected in the definition of sustainable BMs, which comprises a sustainable value proposition, value creation and delivery, and economic value creation under the sustainable management of social, environmental, and economic capital (Schaltegger et al., 2016). Thus, all BM elements (i.e., value proposition, value creation and delivery, and value capture) must be sustainable (Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; França et al., 2017)."	designed around economic, ecological and social value (TBL). All BM elements must be sustainable

Sustainable international business model innovations for a globalizing circular economy: a review and synthesis, integrative framework, and opportunities for future research	Chabowski et al	2023	"A sustainable business model "aim[s] at solutions for [environmental, social, and/or economic] sustainable development by creating additional monetary and non-monetary value" (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018a, 2018b: 713–714)"	aim at solutions for environmental, social and/or economic sustainable development . Create monetary and non-monetary value
Sustainable by design: An organizational design tool for sustainable business model innovation	Coffay and Bocken	2023	"sustainable business models (SBMs), i.e. those which "create significant positive [impact] and/or significantly reduced negative impacts for the environment and society, through changes in the way the organization and its value-network create, deliver value and capture value ... or change their value propositions" (Bocken et al., 2014, p. 44)" "Sustainable business models are distinct from 'conventional' business models insofar as they "incorporate pro-active multi-stakeholder management, the creation of monetary and non-monetary value for a broad range of stakeholders, and hold a long-term perspective" (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018, p. 403–404)."	create significant positive and/or significantly reduced negative impacts for the environment and/or society. Incorporate active multistakeholder management, creation of monetary and non-monetary value for broad range of stakeholders, have long-term perspective
Open strategy and dynamic capabilities: A framework for circular economy business models research	De Angelis et al	2023	"According to Schaltegger et al. (2016), a sustainable BM "helps describing, analyzing, managing and communicating (i) a company's sustainable value proposition to its customers and all other stakeholders, (ii) how it creates and delivers this value, (iii) and how it captures economic value while maintaining or regenerating natural, social and economic capital beyond its organizational boundaries" (p. 4)."	a sustainable BM "helps describing, analyzing, managing and communicating (i) a company's sustainable value proposition to its customers and all other stakeholders, (ii) how it creates and delivers this value, (iii) and how it captures economic value while maintaining or regenerating natural, social and economic capital beyond its organizational boundaries"
Digital sustainable business model innovation: applying dynamic capabilities approach (DSBMI-DC)	Hajihedari et al	2023	"sustainable business models (BM) have become increasingly popular in the first two decades of the 21st century with the vision of realizing sustainable development strategies and endeavours (Szromek, 2021)." "They have attempted to create a sustainable BM by focusing less on short-term profit maximization and more on creating long-term value for all stakeholders, which of course needs fundamental changes in how they conduct business, reflecting their attention to social and environmental issues in addition to economic performance (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018; Bocken et al., 2019)."	focus less on short term profit maximization and more on creating long-term value for all stakeholders, attention to social and environmental issues in addition to economic performance
A systematic review of sustainable business models: Opportunities, challenges, and future research directions	Karuppiah et al	2023	"sustainable business models (SBMs) include environmental and social aspects and economic aspects." "SBMs offer a competitive advantage through multi-stakeholder management, product or process innovation, and effective inventory management [5]." "Most industrial sectors are adopting circular economy (CE) practices, considering it an SBM. However, according to Hina et al. [8]..."	include environmental and social and economic aspects. Offer competitive advantage through multistakeholder management, product or process innovation and effective inventory management. SBM is not just adopting CE principles
Interconnected or Disconnected? A Review of Sustainability, Resilience, and Sustainable Business Model Constructs in the Academic Business Literature	Kassier	2023	"At the heart of sustainable business models is the need for businesses to redefine value in their value proposition, value creation, and value capture processes. This redefining of value must incorporate a system thinking approach in the measurement attached to value (Bocken et al., 2019). Sustainable business models modify the business model concept by incorporating sustainability aspects into the value processes of a firm (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018)."	redefining value by incorporating sustainability aspects into value processes of firm

Towards regenerative business models: A necessary shift?	Konietzko et al	2023	"In their dominant systems view, we find that sustainable business models focus primarily on socio-technical systems, circular business models on closed-loop economic systems, and regenerative business models on social-ecological systems." "In terms of their main goals, sustainable business models focus on the triple bottom line, circular business models on material productivity, and regenerative business models on planetary health and societal wellbeing. We also propose that the design foci of these three perspectives overlap. Sustainable and circular business models share a design focus on the circular technosphere (design for the technical cycle and material productivity), sustainable and regenerative business models share a focus on the sustainable humansphere (design to meet human needs within planetary boundaries) and circular and regenerative business models share a design focus on the regenerative biosphere (design for the biological cycle and ecosystem regeneration)." "The dominant systems view of sustainable business models is on socio-technical systems, primarily product-service systems, and organizational, inter-organizational and societal levels, where nature is referred to in rather abstract terms as the environment (Boons et al., 2013; Stubbs and Cocklin, 2008; Evans et al., 2017). The key focus here is on the need to mitigate negative impacts on the natural environment and communities affected by business operations (Boons and LüdekeFreund, 2013; Boons et al., 2013)." "In terms of their main goals, sustainable business models aim at a balance between economic, social and environmental value creation, the so-called triple bottom line (Bocken et al., 2014; Geissdoerfer et al., 2018a, 2018b; Boons et al., 2013; Joyce and Paquin, 2016; Evans et al., 2017; Upward and Jones, 2016; Boons and Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Stubbs and Cocklin, 2008). Animals and plants are mentioned only in abstract terms as 'the environment' in the seminal articles on sustainable business models."	focus primarily on socio-technical systems. Main goals focus on TBL and balancing it
Defining Value in Sustainable Business Models	Neesham et al	2023	"Although SBMs have been distinguished from traditional business models in many ways, consensus seems established around two key distinctions: (D1) SBMs create value that is not just economic but also social and/or environmental; and (D2) SBMs create value not just for the firm and its customers but for multiple categories of stakeholders (see, for example, Gorissen et al., 2016; Peric et al., 2017; Schaltegger et al., 2012; Stubbs, 2017; Yang, Evans, et al., 2017; Yang, Vladimirova, & Evans, 2017)."	two key distinctions from traditional BM: they create value that is social and/or environmental on top of economic, and they create value not just for firm and customers of firms but for multiple categories of stakeholders
Missing Attention to Power Dynamics in Collaborative Multi-Actor Business Models for Sustainability	Skritsovali et al	2023	"In developing this analysis, SBMs then refer to a system that "helps describing, analysing, managing, and communicating (i) a company's sustainable value proposition to its customers, and all other stakeholders, (ii) how it creates and delivers this value, (iii) and how it captures economic value while maintaining or regenerating natural, social, and economic capital beyond its organizational boundaries" [11]. SBMs adopt both a network-centric and a firm-centric perspective that recognises the mutual interdependencies between those involved in value creation [2]."	a system that "helps describing, analysing, managing, and communicating (i) a company's sustainable value proposition to its customers, and all other stakeholders, (ii) how it creates and delivers this value, (iii) and how it captures economic value while maintaining or regenerating natural, social, and economic capital beyond its organizational boundaries ". they adopt both network-centric and firm-centric perspective that recognized mutual interdependencies between stakeholders involved
Beyond Sustainability, Toward Resilience, and Regeneration: An Integrative Framework for Archetypes of Regenerative Innovation	Yadav, V., Yadav, N.	2024	"Konietzko et al. (2023) offer some foundational differences between circular, sustainable, and regenerative approaches in the context of business models. They suggest that sustainable business models aim to reduce a firm's environmental impact and circular business models enhance resource efficiency and self-sustainability." "Sustainable business models pursue sustainable innovation (Boons & LüdekeFreund, 2013), focusing on reducing, repurposing, or substituting materials for sustainability (Bocken et al., 2014)."	reduce firm's environmental impact, pursue sustainable innovation focusing on reducing, repurposing or substitution

Low-carbon business models: Review and typology	Sairanen et al.	2024	"However, sustainable business models tend to address sustainability on a very general level and emphasize social responsibility (e.g., Evans et al., 2017)." "Sustainable business models aim for value creation in terms of both economic as well as environmental and social benefits (Evans et al., 2017). They "seek to go beyond delivering economic value and include a consideration of other forms of value for a broader range of stakeholders" (Bocken, Short, Rana, & Evans, 2013, p. 484). Employing a system-level perspective alongside a company-level perspective, sustainable business models consider the environment and society to be key stakeholders (Bocken et al., 2014; Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008). Such models typically encompass technological, social, and organizational solutions combined with long-term thinking and multi-stakeholder management (Bocken et al., 2014; Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Geissdoerfer et al., 2018). In practice, sustainable business models may refer to, for instance, efficiency, renewability, servitization, repurposing, or behavioral change (Bocken et al., 2014)." "However, a sustainable business model is a highly general concept for business organizations seeking to achieve multiple social and environmental goals; thus, the concept does not provide a focused or structured explanation of how companies' sustainable business models can contribute to mitigating climate change or carbon emissions."	address sustainability on very general level, emphasize social responsibility. Economic and environmental and social benefits, go beyond just economic value and consider other firms of value for broader range of stakeholders. Employ system-level perspective.
In the eye of the beholder: Stakeholder perceived value in sustainable business models	Norris, S.	2024	"emphasise value creation for the various stakeholders of an organisation (Laasch, 2018; Spieth et al., 2019; Stubbs and Cocklin, 2008)."	emphasize value creation for various stakeholders
In the eye of the beholder: Stakeholder perceived value in sustainable business models	Norris, S.	2024	"with aspired value emphasis on economic, social and environmental aspects"	aspire to create value economically, socially and environmentally
Review and Categorisation of Support Types for Business Model Innovation for Sustainability**	Ademi and Klungseth	2024	"SBM is a BM that incorporates "sustainability as an integral part of the company's value proposition and value creation logic" (Abdelkafi & Täuscher, 2016, p. 75)." "we interpret SBM as sustainable in broader terms, including the economic, social, and environmental pillars of sustainability. [...] SBMs help integrate sustainability at the core of business activities and serve an expanded list of stakeholders, including the environment and society at large (Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008). Stubbs and Cocklin (2008) define SBMs as models "where sustainability concepts shape the driving force of the firm and its decision-making" (p. 103). Abdelkafi and Täuscher (2016) also argue that SBMs "incorporate sustainability as an integral part of the company's value proposition and value creation logic ... [and consequently] ... provide value to the customer and the natural environment or society" (p. 75). Concerning the expanded list of stakeholders, Bocken et al. (2014) argued that SBMs align the "interests of all stakeholder groups and explicitly consider the environment and society as key stakeholders" (p. 44)."	a BM that incorporates sustainable as integral part of value proposition and value creation logic. Economic, social and environmental pillars. Align interests of all stakeholder groups. Environment and society considered as key stakeholders
Sustainable business models: Researchers as design thinkers for problem-driven research	Bastian and Caputo	2024	"Sustainable business models (SBMs) constitute a distinct field of study, characterized by their potential to significantly influence environmental and societal outcomes. They aim to amplify positive and/or minimize negative impacts through innovative shifts in how an organization and its value network create, deliver, and capture value (Bocken et al., 2014; Geissdoerfer et al., 2016). The so-called "SBM approach" predicates the pursuit of economic performance by integrating the preservation and renewal of all resources that allow the business to take place, and by nurturing relationships and interactions between stakeholders (Rosato et al., 2021; Schaltegger et al., 2016)." "Among the many definitions proposed for SBMs (Bocken et al., 2014; Breuer & Lüdeke-Freund, 2014; Schaltegger et al., 2016), we rely on Geissdoerfer et al. (2016) as their definition represents a design context for SBMs. In particular, Geissdoerfer et al. (2016, p.2) define a sustainable business model as a "simplified representation of the elements, the interrelationship between these elements, and the interactions with its stakeholders that an organizational unit uses to create, deliver, capture, and exchange sustainable value.""	aim to amplify positive and/or minimize negative impacts through innovation. Integrates preservation and renewal of resources, nurtures relationships and interactions between stakeholders. Create sustainable value.
Sustainable business models and organizational boundaries—A literature review	Bjartmarz and Bocken	2024	"Although there is not one definition of a sustainable business model (Lozano, 2018), it is clear that it is about value, not only for customers but also for the society, natural environment and other stakeholders such as suppliers, customers, and employees (Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008). Hence, multi-stakeholder management is essential (Evans et al., 2017; Geissdoerfer et al., 2018; Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008), and multiple sustainability values need to be integrated into the business model and value chain (Abdelkafi & Täuscher, 2016; Bocken et al., 2014; Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008)."	creates value for customers, and society, natural env and other stakeholders. Requires multistakeholder management. Integrates sustainability values into BM

Investigating the key success factors within business models that facilitate long-term value creation for sustainability-focused start-ups	Christodoulou et al	2024	"Scholars argue that sustainable business models should not only create value for the company but also contribute positively to societal and environmental wellbeing. López-Nicolás et al. (2021) advocate for the integration of sustainability into innovative business models, highlighting the potential for synergistic outcomes that benefit both the organization and the wider community." "LüdekeFreund (2010) conceptualizes sustainable business models (SBMs) as those that not only create competitive advantage through superior customer value but also contribute to the sustainable development of both the company and society. In a similar vein, Schaltegger et al. (2012) advocate for SBMs that incorporate voluntary activities aimed at addressing social and environmental challenges, thereby generating positive business outcomes. However, despite these conceptualizations, the literature on sustainable business models remains somewhat fragmented, reflecting the complex and multifaceted nature of sustainability within organizational contexts (Bocken et al., 2014)."	should not only create economic value for company but also contribute positively to societal and environmental wellbeing. Contribute to sustainable development of company and society.
Regenerative business strategies: A database and typology to inspire business experimentation towards sustainability	Das and Bocken	2024	"Sustainable business models focus on reducing the footprint and resulting harm of a business model."	focus on reducing footprint and resulting harm of a BM
Design Options for Sustainable and Open Business Models: A Taxonomy-Based Analysis	Mais and Bauernhansl	2024	"A Sustainable Business Model (SBM) describes how companies create, deliver, and maintain value while considering the interests of various stakeholders, the environment, and society [6,10,11]."	describes how companies create, deliver, and maintain value while considering the interests of various stakeholders, the environment, and society
What is unique about sustainable business models for the base of the pyramid?	Mendez-Leon et al	2024	"The SBM is a tool that helps orchestrate the efforts of a variety of stakeholders to address economic, social, and environmental issues and assists companies to transit toward sustainability. Like the BM, the SBM is closely connected to the value concept (Dembek et al., 2022; Morioka et al., 2018; Shakeel et al., 2020), but it integrates a broader range of stakeholders (Fobbe & Hilletoft, 2021) and is expected to create sustainable value (SV); that is, economic, social, and environmental benefits beyond the focal company (Attanasio et al., 2021)."	tool that helps orchestrate efforts of variety of stakeholders to address economic, social and environmental issues. Assists companies shift towards sustainability. Integrates broader range of stakeholders than traditional BM. Creates sustainable value: economic, social and environmental benefits beyond focal company
What is unique about sustainable business models for the base of the pyramid?	Mendez-Leon et al	2024	"SBMs are BMs conceived to provide sustainable (economic, social, and environmental) benefits (Attanasio et al., 2021; Kristensen & Remmen, 2019). SBMs are expected to integrate a broader range of stakeholders than conventional BMs (Fobbe & Hilletoft, 2021; Geissdoerfer et al., 2018). Bocken et al. (2014) identified eight different SBM archetypes. According to these authors, based on the interactions among multiple stakeholders, SBMs develop sustainable value-creation processes that put the focus on society and the environment."	BM that provide sustainable (economic, environmental, social) benefits. Integrate broader range of stakeholders than traditional BM. They develop value-creation processes that put focus on society and environment

Appendix D.2 - Sustainable Business Model Concept Definition Construction

Intent (Why?)	Options	Tally	Combined	Tally
	Reduce firm's environmental impact*	2	Economic, environmental and social benefit/value creation (TBL); sustainable development	37
	Economic, environmental and social benefit/value creation (TBL); sustainable development	37	Create value for consumers, society, natural environment and other stakeholders beyond the organizational boundaries	10
	Increase positive effects and/or significantly reduce negative effects for environment and society*	7	Increase positive effects and/or significantly reduce negative effects for environment and society*	9
	Create value for consumers, society, natural environment and other stakeholders beyond the organizational boundaries	10		

Mechanisms (How?)	Options	Tally	Combined	Tally
	Sustainable innovation	2	Integrate sustainable principles (TBL) into VP and value creation logic/internal commitment	26
	Emphasize social responsibility**	3	Account for and align diverse stakeholder interests (manage), and nurture their relationships and interactions	30
	Consider value creation for broader range of stakeholders*	4	Promote stewardship (social/environmental)	4
	Employ system-level perspective***	2	Consider environment and society as key stakeholders	9
	Integrate sustainable principles (TBL) into VP and value creation logic/internal commitment	26	Employ network-centric and firm-centric perspective	4
	Account for and align diverse stakeholder interests (manage)*	20	Sustainable innovation	2
	Consider environment and society as key stakeholders	9	Long-term perspective	2
	Nurture stakeholder relationships and interactions*	6		
	Promote environmental stewardship**	1		
	Long-term perspective	2		

Constructed Definition:
<p>A Sustainable Business Model (SBM) is a business model that creates, delivers, and captures value while explicitly integrating economic, environmental, and social sustainability goals into its core operations and stakeholder relationships (Méndez-León et al., 2024). SBMs represent a comprehensive reconfiguration of business logic where sustainability is not an add-on but a core design principle that reshapes how value is defined, created, and distributed by the business (Norris, 2024; Turetken et al., 2024). SBMs are sometimes also referred to as Sustainability-Oriented Business Models or Green Business Models, where the former label is used interchangeably with SBM by some works (Boffa & Maffei, 2021; D'Amato et al., 2020), and the latter label tends to be used in policy-related contexts (Solesvik et al., 2022).</p> <p><i>Goals</i> : The primary goal of an SBM is to contribute to sustainable development by generating integrated economic, environmental, and social value, aligning with the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) principle of sustainability (Konietzko et al., 2023). SBMs aim not only to maintain firm profitability but also to reduce negative impacts and increase positive outcomes for society and the natural environment, often seeking to create value beyond organizational boundaries, including for communities, ecosystems, and future generations (Schaltegger et al., 2016).</p> <p><i>Mechanisms</i> : SBMs operationalize their goals by embedding sustainability principles into their value proposition, internal processes, and stakeholder governance. Key mechanisms include aligning and managing diverse stakeholder interests, integrating environmental and social factors into strategic decision-making, and applying a system-level perspective that considers the firm's broader social-ecological context (Boffa & Maffei, 2021; Hernández-Chea et al., 2021; Skritsovali et al., 2023). SBMs adopt a long-term perspective and promote stakeholder stewardship in both environmental and social responsibility.</p> <p><i>Enablers</i> : SBMs are supported by sustainable innovations and organizational tools, including technological and social innovations, new business architectures and models (e.g., product-service systems, bottom-of-the-pyramid models), performance measurement systems based on TBL sustainability metrics, and collaborative value networks that span public, private, and nonprofit actors (Di Tullio et al., 2018; Stubbs & Cocklin, 2008b; Yadav & Yadav, 2024). These enablers help firms implement, monitor, and adapt their sustainability logic across complex, multi-actor business ecosystems.</p>

	Employ both network-centric and firm-centric perspective***	2		
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Enablers (What? Technologies/materials/platforms)	Options	Tally	Combined	Tally
	Innovation (e.g. technological, organizational, social, products and services)(partially or fully replace unsustainable VPs)	5		
	NBMs like product-service-systems, bottom of the pyramid, circular business models	4		
	System of sustainable value flows among multiple stakeholders (incl. environment and society)	4		
	Performance management to assess performance of SBM implementation (based on TBL)	3		
	Sustainable practices/principles, CSR	2		
	Partnerships with public or non-profit actors	1		
	Value network with a new purpose, design and governance	1		
	Contemplation of value creation, value destroyed and value uncaptured	1		
	Information technology to manage and control ecosystem processes at all levels + integrating, analysing and disseminating data and information about resources	1		
	Focus less on short-term profit maximization and more on long-term value for all stakeholders	1		
	Inventory management	1		
	Well-defined norms	1		